

MS6 All data provided to the database, database is operational

Simon Moakes FiBL

The farm characterisation database is constructed from two major data sources, the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN¹), and the Gridded Agro-Meteorological Data in Europe (AGRI4CAST²). The data was processed and is presented as two databases (dairy and beef), as averages for a wide range of variables at a NUTS2³ regional scale.

Detailed FADN data (anonymised individual farm data) was requested for all ruminant and mixed farm types, over 10 years and the most recent data available at request (2004-2013). Following receipt of the data (~250k farms) this has been compiled into two consistent datasets, one for dairy (141,961) farms and one for beef farms (54,417). Each dataset comprises some values directly from the FADN data, but also a large number of calculated variables, to identify dairy or beef enterprise performance at per animal, per output product unit or per hectare. These values were calculated according to the respective dairy and beef enterprise allocation methodologies described by FADN. Further economic and structural variables have been calculated as necessary.

For each farm within the dataset, the structural, production and economic data from the FADN data is supplemented with the addition of meteorological data. The daily meteorological data was downloaded from the AGRI4STAT database web portal at a NUTS2 scale. For each NUTS2 region data was available for a number of weather stations. This large dataset was processed through scripts in STATA software to generate annual values for a wide range of climatic variables, including Temperature Humidity Index (THI), and indicators of drought and seasonality of weather. Furthermore, the altitude values per weather station allowed for a sub-grouping of weather station data by altitude zone (aligned with values available in the FADN dataset).

Using a Latent Class Analysis process, the meteorological data was analysed to identify consistent environmental regions in Europe. Selected climatic variables, together with altitude zone, were utilised to statistically identify differing zones, and to classify each NUTS2 region to a zone, resulting in 6 lowland zones and 3 upland zones (above 600m) The

¹ The Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) is an instrument for evaluating the income of agricultural holdings and the impacts of the Common Agricultural Policy. The concept of the FADN was launched in 1965, when Council Regulation 79/65 established the legal basis for the organisation of the network. (http://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/rca/concept_en.cfm)

² CGMS database contains meteorological parameters from weather stations interpolated on a 25x25 km grid. Meteorological data are available on a daily basis from 1975 to the last calendar year completed. (<http://agri4cast.jrc.ec.europa.eu/DataPortal/Index.aspx>)

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/nuts-maps-.pdf>,
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/principles-and-characteristics>

LCA process enhanced an earlier method of manually overlaying the Metzger et al. (2005⁴) pedo-climatic zone allocation, but closely correlates. Therefore for each farm in the dairy and beef datasets, meteorological and environmental zone data was allocated on a NUTS2 by altitude zone basis.

The dairy and beef datasets of individual farm data are fully operational and are currently being assessed using Latent Class Analysis to classify farms by the farm system characteristics within each environmental zone. Organic farms will be provided as a separate class, as they operate under consistent EU organic standards, as well as differing price structures to conventional farms.

Data Management Plan

The individual farm database is held on secure servers at FiBL and due to the need to protect the identity of farms, and the signed confidentiality agreement with FADN will not be shared with partners. However, descriptive statistics per farm type at NUTS2 level for the dairy and beef datasets will be provided to partners within GenTORE. This allows a full understanding of typical production systems and environmental conditions at a fine scale, supplementing data available through genetic databases and individual farm data, linking to Task 1.3 and 4.2 directly, and other tasks more generally, in explaining regional variations in farm and productivity differences.

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>